

Evaluation of Elastic Local Buckling Strength of Lipped Channel Section Members Considering Shear Bending Interaction

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ABSTRACT

Recently in Japan, thin-walled cold-formed steel with thickness less than 2.3 mm is commonly used in steel houses. Lipped channel section member is one of the typical cross-sections. The members have large width–thickness ratios which cause elastic local buckling. The buckling determines the post-buckling behaviours and ultimate strength. Therefore, it is important to investigate the buckling strength to accurately evaluate the structural performance of the members.

The several previous studies on the elastic local buckling strength of lipped channel section members under shear bending have been conducted. For example, the buckling strength is analytically examined by finite element method. However, the buckling strength is not theoretically examined sufficiently. Especially, the coupled effects of plate elements are not sufficiently understood.

The purpose of this paper is to evaluate the elastic local buckling strength of lipped channel section members under shear bending. The buckling strength of 5 all plate elements is theoretically derived by energy method considering shear bending interaction and coupled effects of plate elements. The effects of loading conditions, member shapes, and boundary conditions (simply supported/considering coupled effects/elastically supported/clamped along longitudinal edges) on the buckling strength and buckling modes are investigated. It is revealed that consideration of coupled effects of plate elements is necessary, and the buckling strength increases due to shear bending interaction and complicatedly changes due to the flange-web and lip-web aspect ratios. Reasonable approximations for the buckling coefficients corresponding to the gradient of bending moment, aspect ratio of member length, and flange-web aspect ratio, and lip-web aspect ratio are presented. Furthermore, using the general-purpose FEM program Abaqus, the elastic buckling modes such as local buckling, distortional buckling, and torsional buckling are also investigated. Finally, the application range of the provided evaluation is defined.

Keywords: Cold-formed steel, Shear bending interaction, Energy method, Finite element method

1 INTRODUCTION

Recently in Japan, thin-walled cold-formed steel of which thickness is less than 2.3 mm has been used in structures such as steel houses. Lipped channel section member is one of the typical cross-sections. The width–thickness ratio is so large that local buckling and distortional buckling occur in the elastic range. Beams and columns are simultaneously affected by shear and bending. Therefore, it is important to reveal the elastic local buckling strength under shear bending.

Furthermore, the elastic buckling affects the post-buckling behaviour. The strength of the cold-formed steel increases after buckling due to the stress redistribution. Kármán et al. (1) refer to

that the strength of thin steel plates under compression increases after elastic local buckling. The ultimate strength of the plates is estimated by the effective width method. Kimura et al. (2) evaluate the ultimate strength of plates under compression, bending, and shear by effective width method. According to the guidelines for thin-walled structures in Japan (3-5), the methods to evaluate the ultimate strength and the methods of allowable stress design are presented by the effective width method. In Eurocode3 (6), effective width method is also presented. Furthermore, Direct Strength Method (DSM) is developed to estimate the ultimate strength of thin-walled members by Schafer (7). In AISI (8), the methods to evaluate the ultimate strength of the members under pure compression, pure bending, and pure shear are presented by DSM. Silvestre et al. (9) investigate the effects of local and distortional coupled geometrical imperfections on the ultimate strength of lipped channel section members under compression for DSM. Furthermore, Pham et al. (10) present advanced DSM including the effects of the gradient of bending moment on the ultimate strength. Both methods are based on the elastic local buckling strength to estimate the post-buckling ultimate strength. From the viewpoint of evaluation of the ultimate strength, it is significantly important to reveal the buckling strength.

Lots of studies on the elastic local buckling strength of plate elements have been conducted. Bleich (11) investigates the buckling strength of plates with elastically restrained longitudinal boundary conditions by energy method. Timoshenko and Gere (12) evaluate the buckling strength of plates with several boundary conditions and under several loading conditions by energy method. Mitsui and Ikarashi (13) evaluate the buckling strength of lipped channel section members under compression by energy method and present the evaluation of the buckling strength. Pham et al. (14) investigate the buckling strength of lipped channel section members under shear bending by employing finite element method (FEM) and finite strip method (FSM) and present the evaluation of the buckling strength.

However, the elastic local buckling strength of the lipped channel section members under shear bending is not sufficiently investigated in the previous studies by theoretical methods. Therefore, the effects of shear bending interaction on the buckling strength is not sufficiently understood.

Then, Sato and Saito (15) reveal the buckling strength of plate elements of lipped channel section members under shear bending by energy method. However, actually, plate elements coupled buckling occurs in the members. It is necessary to present the investigations of the buckling strength considering coupled effects of plate elements. Following them, authors (16) derive the buckling strength of the members considering coupled effects of plate elements under shear bending by energy method. The effects of the loading conditions and member shapes on the buckling strength are revealed. However, any evaluation methods of the buckling strength are not presented.

The purpose of this paper is to present the evaluation method of the buckling strength of lipped channel section members under shear bending sufficiently including the effects of the loading conditions such as the difference of the gradient of bending moment, and the member shape such as the difference of the aspect ratio of member length, the flange-web aspect ratio, and the lip-web aspect ratio on the buckling strength considering the coupled effects of plate elements. In addition, the range of application of the presented evaluation methods are defined.

2 ELASTIC LOCAL BUCKLING ANALYSIS OVERVIEW

2.1 Energy method

Energy method is used in this paper to derive the elastic local buckling strength of lipped channel section members. Fig. 1 shows the analysis model. The parameter L is the member length. The member is subjected to shear bending by the gradient of bending moment β . Fig. 2 shows the cross-section of the member. The member consists of 5 plate elements (1 web, 2 flanges, and 2 lips). The parameter h is the web width, the parameter b is the flange width, the parameter c is the lip width,

and the parameter t is the thickness. The range of investigation of this study includes the cross-sections commonly used in structures ($0.1 \leq b/h \leq 0.5$, $0.05 \leq c/h \leq 0.2$).

To introduce energy method to analyse the buckling strength of the lipped channel section members, functions are defined and shown in Table 1. The parameters a_{mn} to e_{mn} are coefficients used in displacement functions. The function ΔU is the strain energy of all plate elements. The function ΔT is the work of all plate elements done by external force. The functions $\sigma_i(x, y)$ are the normal stress distribution functions which consists of the bending stress distribution and compressive stress distribution. Here, compressive stress is positive. The functions $\tau_i(y)$ are the shear stress distribution functions derived by shear flow theory. The normal stress distribution functions and shear stress distribution functions are the same as that Saito and Sato (15) used. The functions w_i are displacement functions of each plate element. The displacement functions are defined to remain right angle at every joint of adjacent plate elements. The parameter M is the longitudinal half wave number and N is the

Fig. 1 Analysis model

Fig. 2 Cross-section

Table 1 Functions for introduce of energy method

<u>Buckling conditions</u>	
$\left(\frac{\partial \Delta U}{\partial a_{mn}} = \frac{\partial \Delta T}{\partial a_{mn}} \right) \wedge \left(\frac{\partial \Delta U}{\partial b_{mn}} = \frac{\partial \Delta T}{\partial b_{mn}} \right) \wedge \left(\frac{\partial \Delta U}{\partial c_{mn}} = \frac{\partial \Delta T}{\partial c_{mn}} \right) \wedge \left(\frac{\partial \Delta U}{\partial d_{mn}} = \frac{\partial \Delta T}{\partial d_{mn}} \right) \wedge \left(\frac{\partial \Delta U}{\partial e_{mn}} = \frac{\partial \Delta T}{\partial e_{mn}} \right)$	
<u>Strain energy of all plate elements</u>	
$\Delta U = \sum_{i=1}^5 \left[\frac{1}{2} D \int_0^L \int_0^{h,b,c} \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_i}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_i}{\partial y^2} \right)^2 + 2\nu \frac{\partial^2 w_i}{\partial x^2} \frac{\partial^2 w_i}{\partial y^2} + 2(1-\nu) \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_i}{\partial x \partial y} \right)^2 \right\} dx dy \right],$	$D = \frac{Et^3}{12(1-\nu^2)}$
<u>Work done by external force of all plate elements</u>	
$\Delta T = \sum_{i=1}^5 \left[\frac{1}{2} t \int_0^L \int_0^{h,b,c} \left\{ \sigma_i(x, y) \left(\frac{\partial w_i}{\partial x} \right)^2 - 2\tau_i(y) \frac{\partial w_i}{\partial x} \frac{\partial w_i}{\partial y} \right\} dx dy \right]$	
<u>Displacement functions</u>	
$w_1 = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N a_{mn} \mu_m \sin \frac{n\pi(c-y)}{2c} + \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N b_{mn} \mu_m \left(-\frac{c}{b} n \right) \sin \frac{\pi y}{c} \sin \frac{\pi y}{2c}$	
$w_2 = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N a_{mn} \mu_m \left(-\frac{b}{2c} n \right) \sin \frac{\pi y}{b} \cos \frac{\pi y}{2b} + \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N b_{mn} \mu_m \sin \frac{n\pi y}{b} + \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N c_{mn} \mu_m \left(-\frac{b}{h} n \right) \sin \frac{\pi y}{b} \sin \frac{\pi y}{2b}$	
$w_3 = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N b_{mn} \mu_m \frac{h}{b} n \cos(n\pi) \sin \frac{\pi y}{h} \cos \frac{\pi y}{2h} + \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N c_{mn} \mu_m \sin \frac{n\pi y}{h} + \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N d_{mn} \mu_m \left(-\frac{h}{b} n \right) \sin \frac{\pi y}{h} \sin \frac{\pi y}{2h}$	
$w_4 = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N c_{mn} \mu_m \frac{b}{h} n \cos(n\pi) \sin \frac{\pi y}{b} \cos \frac{\pi y}{2b} + \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N d_{mn} \mu_m \sin \frac{n\pi y}{b} + \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N e_{mn} \mu_m \left(-\frac{b}{2c} n \right) \sin \frac{\pi y}{b} \sin \frac{\pi y}{2b}$	
$w_5 = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N d_{mn} \mu_m \frac{c}{b} n \cos(n\pi) \sin \frac{\pi y}{c} \cos \frac{\pi y}{2c} + \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N e_{mn} \mu_m \sin \frac{n\pi y}{2c}$	
<u>Half wave number</u>	
$\mu_m = \begin{cases} \sin \frac{m\pi x}{L} & \text{Simply supported at both ends} \\ \sin \frac{m\pi x}{L} \sin \frac{\pi x}{L} & \text{Clamped at both ends} \end{cases}$	<p>Longitudinal direction $M = 4\lambda$</p> <p>Transverse direction $N = 8$</p>

transverse half wave number. The parameter $\lambda (= L/h)$ is the aspect ratio of member length. In this study, the buckling coefficient represents the buckling strength, and the relationship is given by Eq. (1). The value ${}_b\sigma_{cr}$ is the buckling stress and the value ${}_b k_\sigma$ is the buckling coefficient.

$${}_b\sigma_{cr} = {}_b k_\sigma \frac{\pi^2 E}{12(1 - \nu^2)} \left(\frac{t}{h}\right)^2 \tag{1}$$

2.2 Finite element method

To confirm the validity of analysis results of energy method, to confirm the coupled effects of plate elements, and to investigate the buckling behaviours, finite element analysis is conducted in this paper. Eigenvalue buckling analyses are conducted by the general-purpose FEM program Abaqus. Fig. 3 shows an analysis model. The member is composed of 4-node shell elements. Rigid elements are used to resist warp at both ends. Web is divided into 20 elements along the transverse direction and is divided to make elements nearly square along longitudinal direction. Flange and lip are also divided to make elements nearly square based on the web. Boundary conditions at both ends are as shown in the figure. The external force acts on the centroids of the model section. Here, Young's modulus is 205,000 N/mm², and Poisson's ratio is 0.3.

3 EFFECTS OF LONGITUDINAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS ON ELASTIC LOCAL BUCKLING STRENGTH

It is important to understand the effects of longitudinal boundary conditions on the elastic

Fig. 3 Analysis model for finite element method

Fig. 4 Effects of longitudinal boundary conditions

(A) $b/h = 0.5, c/h = 0.2$

(B) $b/h = 0.3, c/h = 0.1$
Clamped at both ends, $\lambda = 5$,
 $\alpha = 0$ deg., $\beta = 2, p = 0.0$
Fig. 5 Cross-section

local buckling strength. Fig. 4 shows the relationship between the buckling coefficients and the aspect ratios of member length with several longitudinal boundary conditions. The figure shows that the results with elastically supported longitudinal boundary conditions and considering coupled effects of plate elements and FEM are located between the results with simply supported and clamped longitudinal boundary conditions. Furthermore, the results of which boundary conditions is considering coupled effects of plate elements is the most suitable to the results of FEM. This means that it is necessary to consider the coupled effects of plate elements. Fig. 5 shows the cross-section deformations. The sections are located at the maximum displacement position. The results considering coupled effects of plate elements show almost the same deformations to that of FEM. Subsequent investigations are based on the results of considering coupled effects of plate elements by energy method.

4 EFFECTS OF LOADING CONDITIONS ON ELASTIC LOCAL BUCKLING STRENGTH

It is important to understand the effects of loading conditions on the elastic local buckling strength. Fig. 6 shows the relationship between the buckling coefficients and the aspect ratios of the member length. The gradient of bending moment is selected as the parameters in the figure. The member is under antisymmetric bending when the gradient of bending moment is 2, under one end bending when the value is 1, and under pure bending when the value is 0 (Fig. 1). The figure shows that when the member is under antisymmetric bending and the aspect ratio of member length is small, the buckling coefficients are smaller than that under pure bending. This is because the effect of shear is dominant compared to bending. Fig. 7 shows the buckling waveforms. When the effect of shear is dominant, the buckling waveform becomes shear type as shown in Fig. 7(a). Furthermore, the aspect ratio of member length under one end bending where the buckling coefficients become smaller than that under pure bending is smaller than that under antisymmetric bending. This is because the larger the gradient of bending moment becomes, the larger the effect of shear becomes. When the member is under antisymmetric bending and the aspect ratio of member length is large, the buckling coefficients are larger than that under pure bending. This is the results of shear bending interaction, and the effect of bending is dominant compared to shear. Therefore, the buckling waveform becomes bending type as shown in Fig. 7(b). When the member is under one end bending, the effect of bending

Fig. 6 Effects of gradient of bending moment

Fig. 7 Buckling waveforms
Clamped at both ends, $b/h = 0.3, c/h = 0.1,$
 $\alpha = 0 \text{ deg.}, p = 0.0$

is dominant with the smaller aspect ratio of the member length than that under antisymmetric bending as shown in Fig. 7(c). Furthermore, the larger the aspect ratio of member length becomes, the smaller the effect of shear on the buckling strength becomes.

5 EFFECTS OF MEMBER SHAPES ON ELASTIC LOCAL BUCKLING STRENGTH

5.1 Effect of flange-web aspect ratio on elastic local buckling strength

It is important to understand the effect of flange-web aspect ratio on the elastic local buckling strength. Fig. 8 shows the relationship between the buckling coefficients and the flange-web aspect ratios. The common lip-web aspect ratio 0.1 is selected in the figure. The aspect ratios of the member length are selected as 5, 10, 15, and 20, and the loading conditions are also selected as pure bending, one end bending, and antisymmetric bending. The figure shows that buckling coefficients decrease when the flange-web aspect ratios increase. The decreasing curves of the buckling coefficients have inflection points when the flange-web aspect ratio is around 0.5. This is because the change from web local buckling and lip local buckling to flange local buckling due to the increase of the flange width-thickness ratio which can be the factor to make flange local buckling easily occur following to the increase of the flange-web aspect ratio. When the flange-web aspect ratio is over around 0.5, due to flange local buckling occurring and increase of the flange-web aspect ratios, the buckling coefficients

Fig. 8 Effects of flange-web aspect ratio

Fig. 10 Effects of lip-web aspect ratio

Fig. 9 Flange local buckling waveforms

Fig. 11 Lip local buckling waveforms

decrease. Fig. 9 shows that the flange local buckling waveforms. The buckling waveform occurs in the part of flange in compression as shown in the figure.

5.2 Effect of lip-web aspect ratio on elastic local buckling strength

It is important to understand the effect of lip-web aspect ratio on the elastic local buckling strength. Fig. 10 shows the relationship between the buckling coefficients and the lip-web aspect ratios. The common flange-web aspect ratio 0.3 is selected in the figure. The aspect ratios of the member length are selected as 5, 10, 15, and 20 and the loading conditions are also selected as pure bending, one end bending, and antisymmetric bending. The figure shows that the buckling coefficients keep the values when the lip-web aspect ratios are smaller than 0.2. This is because the buckling strength is determined by web local buckling. On the other hand, the buckling coefficients decrease when the lip-web aspect ratios increase from 0.2 to 0.4. This is because lip local buckling occurs when the lip-web aspect ratio is around 0.2. Fig. 11 shows the lip local buckling waveforms. The buckling waveform occurs in the part of lip in compression as shown in the figure. Fig. 10 shows that the buckling coefficients increase when the lip-web aspect ratios increase more than 0.4.

6 EVALUATION OF ELASTIC LOCAL BUCKLING STRENGTH UNDER SHEAR BENDING

The effects of loading conditions depending on the gradient of bending moment and the member shapes such as the aspect ratio of member length, the flange-web aspect ratio, and the lip-web aspect ratio on the elastic local buckling strength of lipped channel section members considering coupled effects of plate elements are revealed. Based on them, evaluation of the buckling strength of the members under shear bending is presented. For the evaluation of the buckling strength under shear bending, the buckling strength under pure bending should be firstly presented. Secondary, the effects of shear bending interaction on the buckling strength is revealed and presented. Finally the evaluation method of the buckling strength under shear bending is presented.

6.1 Evaluation of elastic local buckling strength under pure bending

Evaluation of the elastic local buckling strength under pure bending is presented. Referring to Fig. 6, the buckling coefficients under pure bending are sufficiently convergent when the aspect ratio of the member is longer than 10. Then, the evaluation of the buckling strength under pure bending is presented with the result of the analysis when the aspect ratio of member length is 10. The results are shown in Fig. 12 for each cross-section with the flange-web aspect ratio on the horizontal axis and the lip-web aspect ratio on the vertical axis. The results of evaluations of the buckling coefficients

Clamped at both ends, $\lambda = 10$, $\alpha = 0$ deg., $\beta = 0$, $p = 0.0$

Fig. 12 Evaluation of buckling coefficients under pure bending

Fig. 13 Rate of increase of buckling stress under shear bending to that under pure bending

under pure bending are shown in Fig. 6 with rigid lines. The results suggest that reasonable approximation of the buckling coefficients under pure bending can be obtained.

6.2 Evaluation of elastic local buckling strength under shear bending

To evaluate the effect of shear bending interaction on the buckling strength, the rate of increase of the buckling strength under shear bending to that under pure bending is shown in Fig. 13 with the normalized gradient of bending moment β/λ on the horizontal axis. The rate of increase of the buckling strength has nonlinear relationship to the normalized gradient of bending moment for

Clamped at both ends, $\alpha = 0 \text{ deg.}, p = 0.0$
Fig. 14 Coefficient A in Eq. (2)

Clamped at both ends, $\lambda = 10$
 $\alpha = 0 \text{ deg.}, \beta = 2, p = 0.0$
Fig. 15 Buckling modes

(a) Effect of flange-web aspect ratio

(b) Effect of lip-web aspect ratio

Fig. 16 Ratio of the analysis results of FEM to that of theoretical analyses by energy method

each cross-section. In addition, the rate of increase of the buckling strength is 1.0 when the normalized gradient of the bending moment is 0.0. Then, the approximation of the rate of increase can be expressed by Eq. (2).

$${}_b\sigma_{cr}/{}_b\sigma_{cr\beta 0} = -A(\beta/\lambda)^2 + 2(\beta/\lambda) + 1 \quad (2)$$

The value ${}_b\sigma_{cr\beta 0}$ is the buckling stress under pure bending. The coefficient A should be given for each cross-section. Fig. 14 shows the value of the coefficient A . The results of evaluation of Eq. (2) are shown in Fig. 13 with dotted lines. The results suggest that reasonable buckling coefficients under shear bending can be obtained by Eq. (2).

7 EFFECTS OF LOADING CONDITIONS AND MEMBER SHAPES ON ELASTIC BUCKLING MODES

Buckling modes of the lipped channel section members are affected by the loading conditions and the member shapes. Actually, web local buckling, flange local buckling, lip local buckling, distortional buckling, and torsional buckling can occur in the members. They can occur separately or simultaneously corresponding to the loading conditions and the member shapes. It is important to understand the buckling modes under shear bending. This investigation shows the range of application of the presented evaluation method. To investigate the buckling modes and buckling strength, FEM eigenvalue buckling analysis is conducted.

Fig. 15 shows the elastic buckling modes with the aspect ratio of member length is 10 under antisymmetric bending. The figure shows that web local buckling occurs in the common cross-section. Distortional buckling simultaneously occurs with local buckling when the lip-web aspect ratio is smaller than 0.2. Torsional buckling separately or simultaneously occurs when the flange-web aspect ratio is smaller than about 0.2. Fig. 16 shows the ratio of the analysis results of FEM which do not show the local buckling to that of energy method (EM). Here, pure distortional buckling and couple of distortional buckling and torsional buckling do not appear when the member is under antisymmetric bending. Referring to Fig. 16(a), the ratio dramatically dropped when the flange-web aspect ratio is smaller than 0.2. This is because torsional buckling occurs separately or simultaneously. When the flange-web aspect ratio increases from 0.3, the buckling strength decreases about 20 to 30% to the results of energy method. This is because distortional buckling occurs. Next, Fig. 16(b) shows that the buckling strength decreases when the lip-web aspect ratio decreases to 0.05. This is because distortional buckling occurs separately or simultaneously.

Based on the abovementioned information, the range of application of the presented evaluation by Eq. (2) is defined as flange-web aspect ratio larger than 0.2 and lip-web aspect ratio larger than 0.05.

8 CONCLUSIONS

The elastic local buckling strength of lipped channel section members under shear bending considering coupled effects of plate elements is derived by energy method. The effects of longitudinal boundary conditions on the buckling strength are investigated. The validity of the analysis results is confirmed through comparison to the results of FEM. The effects of loading conditions on the buckling strength are investigated. Furthermore, the effects of the member shapes such as flange-web aspect ratio and the lip-web aspect ratio on the buckling strength are also investigated. From the above investigations, the evaluation method of the buckling strength is presented. The reasonable evaluation of the buckling strength corresponding to the gradient of bending moment, the aspect ratio of member length, the flange-web aspect ratio, and the lip-web aspect ratio becomes possible. In addition, the elastic buckling behaviours including local buckling, distortional buckling, and torsional buckling for each loading condition and member shape are revealed by FEM. Finally, the range of the application

of the presented evaluation method is defined. This evaluation method can contribute the design method of the ultimate post-buckling strength evaluation based on the elastic local buckling strength considering shear bending interaction and coupled effects of plate elements.

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